

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE MIDDLE CORRIDOR – GEORGIA’S ECONOMIC POTENTIAL ON THE NEW SILK ROAD

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Abstract

The Middle Corridor (Trans-Caspian International Transport Route) serves as one of the main trade links between China and Europe, passing through Georgia, Azerbaijan, and Kazakhstan. The network of rail, road, and maritime transport routes traversing Georgia provides a relatively shorter and more efficient trade corridor. The importance of the Middle Corridor has particularly increased following Russia’s invasion of Ukraine, making it an attractive alternative for international trade. Although the corridor is developing rapidly, it still faces infrastructural and geopolitical challenges that require increased investment and deeper economic and trade cooperation with the countries participating in the New Silk Road.

The paper aims to assess Georgia’s economic potential along the Middle Corridor route, focusing on its strategic role, trade opportunities, and infrastructural development. The study combines theoretical analysis with empirical data-based assessments, providing a foundation for defining Georgia’s long-term development prospects in the context of the New Silk Road.

Keywords: Middle Corridor, New Silk Road, International Trade, Georgia, China.

Introduction. Modern geopolitical processes have significantly transformed the logistics landscape of Central Asia. Traditional routes, such as the Trans-Siberian Corridor passing through Russia, have become less viable, which has strengthened the role of new alternatives, including the Trans-Caspian Corridor (TCC). The Middle Corridor is gaining strategic importance as one of the shortest and most reliable routes connecting Central Asia and China with Europe.

According to the World Bank’s 2023 report, Russia’s invasion of Ukraine has increased interest in the Middle Corridor as an intercontinental trade route that can ensure economic resilience and adaptation to a changing geopolitical context. Nevertheless, from a trade and financial perspective, the Middle Corridor primarily offers opportunities for diversifying trade routes and enhanced connectivity among Azerbaijan, Georgia, and Kazakhstan. It may also become a platform for expanding and diversifying trade among the countries participating in the New Silk Road. The World Bank report distinguishes between (1) transcontinental shipments, for which multiple competitive routes exist, including maritime ones, and (2) regional shipments, which are comparatively more relevant to the Middle Corridor (World Bank, 2023).

The study aims to identify Georgia’s economic potential and competitive advantages in the development of the Middle Corridor, as well as to determine the factors that define the country’s role within the Eurasian transport and trade network.

Methodology. The research employs a mixed-methodological approach that combines theoretical and analytical analysis with statistical analysis. The study reviews both Georgian and foreign-language literature

related to the research topic, including academic works, studies, and reports by international organizations and research institutes.

Literature Review. Due to its geopolitical location, Georgia has historically served as a significant transit country and connecting corridor between the West and the countries of Central Asia. This position offers the country significant opportunities to play a crucial role in shaping the global civilization process (Abashishvili et al., 2022).

Russia’s war in Ukraine and the economic sanctions imposed on Russia by the West have contributed to the activation of the “Middle Corridor” project, which will connect China and the countries of Central Asia to Europe (Papava, 2024).

The multimodal middle corridor is a historical opportunity for Georgia, as the development of the middle corridor has enormous economic and financial potential for Georgia (Adeishvili & al., 2025).

From China’s Belt and Road Initiative to the Development Road and the India-Middle East-Europe Economic Corridor, these projects facilitate not only the movement of goods but also the exchange of energy, information, and services across regions (Reisinezhad & al., 2025).

Moreover, the corridor holds particular significance in terms of expanding economic and political cooperation, organizing logistics processes flexibly, and promoting a culture of peace and partnership (Gasimli et al., 2025).

The geo-economic importance of the Middle Corridor has grown notably in recent years against the backdrop of global political and economic shifts. As Aguiar (2025) notes, the decline of Russia’s influence

and the disruption of the Northern Corridor have made the creation of new alternatives within the Asia–Europe transport architecture inevitable. In this process, the Middle Corridor occupies a central position as a system of rail, road, and maritime transport connecting Asia and Europe through Central Asia, the Caspian Sea, Georgia, and the Black Sea.

According to the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD, 2023), the Middle Corridor has become one of the most promising routes across the Eurasian space, especially after 2022, when freight volumes through Russia significantly decreased. This transformation presents Georgia with a unique opportunity to become a regional transport, logistics, and energy hub on the eastern coast of the Black Sea.

Georgia's strategic location, at the crossroads between Europe and Asia, has historically defined its economic function. As the World Bank (2023) points out, Georgia's transit potential is determined not only by geographic factors but also by critical elements such as infrastructure reforms, simplification of customs procedures, and regional integration. As of 2023, the volume of transit cargo passing through Georgia increased by approximately 35% compared to the previous year (ADB, 2023), indicating the growing functional importance of the corridor.

Ekşi and Bayraktar (2022) emphasize that the economic impact of the Middle Corridor on Georgia extends beyond the transport sector. It also contributes to improving the investment climate and enhancing regional cooperation, particularly with Azerbaijan and Kazakhstan. In their view, Georgia serves as an “international trade platform” linking the Caspian and Black Sea markets.

The Georgian Economic Policy Research Center (2023) highlights that the country's diversified infrastructure, including railways, highways, ports, and airports, provides not only transit benefits but also contributes to local economic development, employment

growth, and investment attraction. Furthermore, the modernization of the Anaklia Deep-Sea Port and the national railway system significantly influence Georgia's export capacity and transit revenues (GEPRC, 2023).

Georgia's role in the Middle Corridor is closely linked to energy security and the development of green logistics. The OECD (2024) emphasizes that Georgia could become a carrier of renewable energy within regional networks, further strengthening its economic function. Likewise, Giguashvili and Sadagashvili (2025) note that Georgia's political stability and international cooperation have enabled the country to position itself as a reliable partner within the New Silk Road network.

According to assessments by international financial institutions, Georgia's economic and political environment is a crucial factor in the success of the Middle Corridor (World Bank, 2023; EBRD, 2023). The country's transparent business climate, low bureaucracy, and free trade agreements with the EU, China, and EFTA enhance its investment attractiveness. Consequently, Georgia is gradually transforming not only into a transit space but also into an active participant in regional economic integration.

The analysis of the literature reveals that Georgia's role in the Middle Corridor is twofold: on the one hand, the country benefits economically from increased trade and investment flows; on the other hand, it serves as an essential link for the stability of the Eurasian trade and energy network. Accordingly, Georgia's policy directions and infrastructure development strategies determine not only the country's economic future but also the long-term viability of the Middle Corridor.

Results/Discussion. Thus, the Middle Corridor offers opportunities for route diversification through Georgia's Black Sea ports or via Turkey, with the potential for further expansion into the European Union and the Balkan markets (OECD, 2023).

Figure 1. Middle Corridor Schematic Routes

Source: OECD analysis (2023)

Over the years, significant progress has been made in strengthening the Middle Corridor by improving infrastructure capacity, simplifying railway procedures, establishing integrated services, and ensuring competitive tariffs. Containerized trade between China and Eu-

rope is undergoing diversification, replacing the northern route that passes through Russia. In addition, the Middle Corridor is increasingly positioning itself to capture a larger share of overland freight traffic (Middle Corridor, 2024).

Figure 2. Middle Corridor Container Traffic, thousand TEU

Source: <https://middlecorridor.com/en/>

Building on long-standing and reliable partnerships with countries along the corridor, Georgia continues to enhance transport connectivity by improving both infrastructure and “soft” procedures to facilitate the movements of cargo across borders.

In recent years, growth has been observed in international cargo transportation, averaging 9% in 2021-2024 (ECONOMIC OUTLOOK OF GEORGIA, 2025).

Figure 3. International Cargo Transportation

Source: <https://www.gov.ge/>

Georgia has long served as a reliable transit partner for energy resources, playing a vital role in the South Caucasus Energy Corridor by ensuring the secure and uninterrupted flow of natural gas and crude oil to regional and EU markets by utilizing major trans-

border pipelines for oil and gas, including WREP, BTC, SCP, and NSGP. This strategic position significantly contributes to the energy security of Georgia, neighboring countries, and the European Union.

Figure 4. Natural Gas Transit, mln. m³

Source: <https://www.gov.ge/>

According to the Government of Georgia statement (ECONOMIC OUTLOOK OF GEORGIA, 2025), amid evolving global energy dynamics, the importance of energy security and the expansion of renewable energy sources has grown substantially. In this context, Georgia's role as a dependable transit hub and future supplier of green energy to the EU is becoming increasingly prominent. The country remains firmly committed to strengthening its position as the EU's trusted energy transit partner and a key player within the broader regional transport and energy network.

Georgia's energy security and independence will be considerably strengthened through the implementation of the Black Sea Submarine Cable Project (BSSC). The BSSC aims to connect the power systems of Georgia, Azerbaijan, Romania, and Hungary via a 1,155 km long high-voltage submarine transmission cable with a capacity of 1,300 MW across the Black Sea (Giguashvili & Makasarashvili, 2024).

Although Georgia does not possess abundant energy reserves, its geopolitical location grants it a significant role as a transit country for electricity and gas between Europe and Asia (Salkhinashvili & Giguashvili, 2023).

In light of recent developments, countries must focus their efforts on conserving fossil fuels, investing in energy efficiency, and supporting the increase of renewable energy's share within the energy system. In 2022, significant achievements were recorded worldwide. Hundred pension funds monitored by UNCTAD improved their investments in renewable energies and managed to divest from fossil fuels. Two-thirds of hedge funds have committed to being fossil fuel-free in

their investment portfolios by 2050 (Giguashvili et al., 2023).

Our country's potential allows for the development not only of water resources but also of wind, solar, geothermal, and biomass energy.

Georgia's competitiveness as a maritime nation will be significantly enhanced by the Anaklia Deep-Sea Port, whose preparatory works for the design and construction of marine infrastructure are concluding. The marine infrastructure works are scheduled for completion in 2027. Phase one of the Anaklia Deep Sea Port shall have a minimum capacity to handle 600 thousand TEUs per annum, with tentative CAPEX of USD 600 million. Plans also include creating a free industrial zone and developing a logistics zone for industrial production near the port, which will generate additional jobs and attract investments (ECONOMIC OUTLOOK OF GEORGIA, 2025).

Public data on transit flows through the Middle Corridor are often incomplete, but it is clear that this route is becoming increasingly important as an alternative to traditional trade routes. The route begins in China, where goods are loaded onto railway trains. The cargo moves westward across Kazakhstan and is then transferred to maritime vessels at Kazakhstan's Caspian Sea ports, which cross the Caspian Sea. The cargo arrives in Azerbaijan, where it continues overland toward Europe. Azerbaijan's relatively modern railway infrastructure, including the Baku International Sea Trade Port and the Baku–Tbilisi–Kars (BTK) railway, facilitates the smooth movement of cargo (World Bank, 2023).

Map 1. The MC among trade corridors connecting Europe and Asia
 Source: The World Bank 2023

The Baku–Tbilisi–Kars (BTK) railway, connecting Azerbaijan, Georgia, and Turkey, is a crucial link in the regional railway network, ensuring the rapid transit of cargo to Turkey and European networks. Initially, it was designed to handle 6.5 million tons of cargo annually. But by 2034, its capacity is expected to increase to 17 million tons, significantly enhancing the logistical potential of the Middle Corridor (Aguar, 2025).

The Middle Corridor’s potential lies in the integrated use of rail, maritime, and road transport net-

works, creating flexibility that allows cargo to be redirected in response to changing demand, seasonal disruptions, and geopolitical shifts. Efforts are actively underway to develop logistics hubs, coordinate customs procedures, and implement trade facilitation initiatives aimed at increasing efficiency and strengthening the corridor’s competitiveness.

It is noteworthy that Transit freight clearly dominates over domestic trade, highlighting the crucial role of the Middle Corridor in increasing cargo flows through Georgia.

Figure 5. International Freight (Railway) Railway - International Freight (Thousand Tonnes)
 Source: National Statistics Office of Georgia

Between 2017 and 2024, road freight transit increased significantly, far exceeding the volume of cargo transported by rail.

Figure 6. International Freight (Road Transport) Road Transport - International Freight (Thousand Tonnes)
Source: National Statistics Office of Georgia

The Middle Corridor has significant potential to generate fiscal and economic benefits. Alongside the growth of regional and transit trade transactions through the corridor, an increase in customs revenues is also expected. Increased activities by logistics service providers, port operators, and railway companies automatically have a positive impact on business turnover and the creation of new jobs. That, in turn, will raise contributions from income tax, VAT, and other types of taxes. According to World Bank calculations, improved logistics and infrastructure are expected to increase cargo volumes in Azerbaijan, Georgia, and Kazakhstan by 44% by 2030, which is directly linked to higher fiscal revenues.

A key factor in the development of the Middle Corridor is developing appropriate infrastructure, which, in turn, requires additional investment. The World Bank estimates that approximately \$28 billion will be needed over the next 15 years to develop the Middle Corridor's infrastructure. This infrastructure includes land, rail, and port transport, as well as the development of border crossing points and the implementation of relevant systems. A primary challenge remains the digitization of customs procedures and the adoption of new technologies. According to studies by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2023), the main challenges for mobilizing private capital for corridor development include limited private sector participation in strategic discussions and a lack of public-private partnership projects in transport and logistics.

As a result of Georgia's signing of the Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area (DCFTA) with the European Union in 2014 and a Free Trade Agreement with China in 2017, Georgia has access to a combined consumer market of over two billion people, making it a unique hub on the Middle Corridor route. Despite these market access opportunities, Georgia still experiences a trade deficit. Exports account for 52.8% of GDP, while imports account for 63%. In comparison,

Kazakhstan and Azerbaijan maintain export-oriented trade systems. In Kazakhstan, exports are 42.1% of GDP and imports 26%, while in Azerbaijan, exports account for 60% and imports 27% (Sharashenidze & Cherkezishvili, 2025).

It is notable that, compared to Kazakhstan and Azerbaijan, Georgia's economy is more dependent on imports. However, due to its strategic location, the country can play a crucial role in the development of the Middle Corridor.

Conclusion. The Middle Corridor has already become an alternative trade route connecting Asia and Europe. In recent years, its development has significantly contributed to the growth of cargo volumes and customs revenues in Georgia, Kazakhstan, and Azerbaijan. The corridor's potential offers opportunities for Georgia's further economic development, including the creation of new jobs and expanded access to global markets. The prospects for the Middle Corridor's development largely depend on investments from the countries participating in the Silk Road, political stability, mutual trust among the parties, and the international environment, which researchers and policymakers currently describe as an era of uncertainty.

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